

Temperature Effect on the Molecular Solution Volumes of Urea, Potassium Iodide, Potassium Chloride, and Potassium Chromate

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The densities of urea, KI, KCl, and K_2CrO_4 have been determined at various temperatures and the molecular solution volumes calculated. Results show that the molecular solution volume, ${}_mV_s$, increases with rise in temperature and is a linear function of $T^3/3$, where T is the temperature in degree centigrade.

Schmidt¹ observed that when a solute dissolved in water, there was a change in volume. The volume occupied by a g. mole of solute while in a state of solution is known as 'molecular solution volume'. Schmidt proposed the following expression for the molecular solution volume:

$${}_mV_s = \frac{aq}{d_s} + \alpha - \frac{aq}{d_w} \quad (i)$$

where α is the molecular weight of the anhydrous salt; d_s , the density of the salt solution; d_w , the density of water; aq is the weight of water present to each molecule of the salt. If ρ is the weight of the solute in g., dissolved in water to a final volume of 100 ml, then

$$aq = \frac{(100 d_s - \rho) \alpha}{\rho} \quad (ii)$$

He found that the molecular solution volume of the dissolved salt decreased with the rising dilution till a limit was reached at which it remained practically constant. The same expression was corroborated by Traube²⁻⁵ who made the determination of the molecular solution volume for a large number of electrolytes and non-electrolytes. Datta and Dhar⁶ have calculated the molecular solution volumes of a few electrolytes at different concentrations. Determination of molecular solution volumes of isobutyl (+)-tartrate and isobutyl (-)-tartrate in a symmetrical solvent, nitrobenzene, and in an asymmetrical solvent, 1-menthyl acetate, was carried out by Patterson and Lambertson⁷ and later by Banks⁸. Scott^{9,10} and Gucker¹¹ defined 'apparent molal volume' and 'apparent molal solute property'.

1. *Monatsh.*, 1890, 11, 35.
2. *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 2527.
3. *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 3173.
4. *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 410.
5. *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 2722.
6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 1303.
7. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1453.
8. *Ibid.*, 1937, 185.
9. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, 38, 951.
10. *Ibid.*, 1935, 39, 1031.
11. *Ibid.*, 1934 38, 307, 319.

In this communication our results on the careful determination of molecular solution volumes of urea, KI, KCl, and K_2CrO_4 at three different concentrations and various temperatures are recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL

All solutions were made in double distilled water. The densities at different temperatures were determined by using density bottles at temperatures maintained constant with the help of a thermomix. The molecular solution volumes were calculated from equations (i) and (ii). The values of mV_s are accurate up to the second place of decimal. Results are recorded in Tables I-IV.

TABLE I
Urea (M.W. 60.572).

Temp.	Density of water.	Conc. = 1.0M		Conc. = 3.0M	
		Density.	mV_s .	Density.	mV_s .
25°	0.9951	1.0107	44.68 ml	1.0424	44.51 ml
30°	0.9940	1.0095	44.83	1.0401	44.96
35°	0.9925	1.0078	45.10	1.0378	45.30
40°	0.9905	1.0055	45.49	1.0352	45.59
45°	0.9887	1.0035	45.80	1.0327	45.91
50°	0.9842	0.9991	45.88	1.0285	46.02

TABLE II
Potassium iodide (M.W. 166.016).

Temp.	Density of water.	Conc. = 1.0M		Conc. = 3.0M	
		Density.	mV_s .	Density.	mV_s .
25°	0.9953	1.1144	47.14 ml	1.3460	47.35 ml
30°	0.9940	1.1125	47.70	1.3445	49.48
35°	0.9924	1.1098	48.99	1.3427	49.63
40°	0.9906	1.1079	49.18	1.3396	50.15
45°	0.9880	1.1049	49.71	1.3363	50.52
50°	0.9851	1.1016	50.27	1.3331	50.77
55°	0.9820	1.0980	50.93	1.3288	51.34
60°	0.9777	1.0934	51.46	1.3241	51.70
65°	0.9720	1.0879	51.56	1.3190	51.80
70°	0.9668	1.0828	51.74	1.3145	51.84

TABLE III
Potassium chloride (M.W. 74.556).

Temp.	Density of water.	Conc. = 1.0M		Conc. = 2.0M		Conc. = 3.0M	
		Density	mV_s .	Density.	mV_s .	Density.	mV_s .
30°	0.9946	1.0400	29.31 ml	1.0835	30.27 ml	1.1231 ml	31.22 ml
35°	0.9930	1.0380	29.77	1.0814	30.57	1.1235	31.28
40°	0.9901	1.0351	29.85	1.0786	30.61	1.1202	31.50
45°	0.9886	1.0334	30.09	1.0763	31.06	1.1183	31.68
50°	0.9866	1.0314	30.18	1.0742	31.17	1.1163	31.75
55°	0.9837	1.0278	30.96	1.0713	31.27	1.1136	31.77
60°	0.9789	1.0230	31.08	1.0665	31.38	1.1091	31.83
65°	0.9761	1.0201	31.30	1.0638	31.46	1.1064	31.89
70°	0.9727	1.0163	31.83	1.0603	31.82	1.1033	31.90

TABLE IV

Potassium chromate (M.W. 194.202).

Temp.	*Density of water.	Conc. = 1.0M		Conc. = 1.5M		Conc. = 2.0M	
		Density.	mV_s	Density.	mV_s	Density.	mV_s
20°	0.9998	1.1295	48.61 ml	1.2092	51.47 ml	1.2745	54.10 ml
25°	0.9991	1.1298	49.84	1.2075	51.63	1.2736	54.32
30°	0.9983	1.1295	49.53	1.2054	51.92	1.2719	54.83
35°	0.9979	1.1234	50.26	1.2026	52.45	1.2661	55.26
40°	0.9974	1.1216	50.64	1.2007	52.67	1.2662	55.50
45°	0.9969	1.1240	51.02	1.1972	52.92	1.2639	55.59
50°	0.9963	1.1247	51.10	1.1938	53.10	1.2599	55.63
55°	0.9754	1.1196	51.26	1.1867	53.31	1.2561	55.72
70°	0.9727	1.1165	51.62	1.1862	53.32	1.2529	56.06

* V_s values in the densities of water in the tables are due to errors in measurements.

DISCUSSION

We find that the molecular solution volume, mV_s , increases with the rise in temperature and is a linear function of $T^{3/2}$, where T is the temperature in °C. From our results, we see that

(a) The mV_s of urea is 44.68 ml at 25° and 45.88 ml at 50° for 1.0 M concentration, showing an increase of about 2.6% for a 25°-change in temperature.

(b) The mV_s of KI is 47.70 ml at 30° and 50.93 ml at 55° for 1.0 M concentration, showing an increase of about 6.6% for a 25°-change in temperature.

(c) The mV_s of KCl is 29.31 ml at 30° and 30.96 ml at 55° for 1.0 M concentration, showing an increase of about 5.6% for a 25°-change in temperature.

(d) The mV_s of K_2CrO_4 is 48.61 ml at 30° and 51.02 ml at 55° for 1.0 M concentration, showing an increase of about 4.9% for a 25°-change in temperature.

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